

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART XVI

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Synthesis of thiazylaminoquinoline derivatives containing tertiary basic groups in the 3-position is described.

Part XV (Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 676) describes the preparation of 6-(thiazyl-2'-) amino-4-piperidino-2-methylquinoline, which has been synthesised with the object of finding whether such a type of compound possesses any antispasmodic activity. In view of the recent observations that antispasmodics are, in general, salts of tertiary bases, it has been considered desirable to extend the range of such compounds and to incorporate basic groups into 6 (thiazyl-2'-) amino-4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline.

According to the present knowledge of the Mannich reaction (Blicke, "Organic Reactions", Vol. I, 1942; Burckhalter *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1363; Burckhalter, *ibid.*, 1950, 72, 1308), the condensation of substituted phenols with formaldehyde and secondary amines gives rise to corresponding *o*-cresol derivatives. In studying the Mannich reaction with 3-hydroxy-6-methylpyridine derivatives, Stempel and Buzzi (*ibid.*, 1949, 71, 2969) have shown that the basic group enters the 2-position. Price and Jackson (*ibid.*, 1946, 68, 1282) have similarly observed that the Mannich reaction with 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline involves incorporation of the basic group in the 3-position.

It has now been found that 6-(thiazyl-2'-)amino-4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline, described in part XV (Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), condenses with formaldehyde and a secondary amine. In view of the above findings, the basic group has undoubtedly entered the 3-position to yield the compound (I, R=piperidino or diethylamino group.) With phosphorus oxychloride the compound (I) furnishes the corresponding 4-chloro derivative (II).

The compound (I) has also been obtained in the following manner: 6-Acetylamino-4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline (Kermack and Weatherhead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 563; Jacini, *Gazzetta*, 1941, 71, 53) has now been condensed with formaldehyde and a secondary amine to give the compound (III), in which the basic group has likewise entered the 3-position. On hydrolysis, the corresponding 6-amino derivative (IV) has been obtained, dihydrochloride of which, when reacted with potassium thiocyanate, has

yielded the thiocyanate (cf. McCrosky *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 722; Hurd and Wehrmeister, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 1407) of the corresponding 6-thiocarbamido derivative (V). The interaction of (V) with $\alpha\beta$ -dichlorodiethyl ether has furnished the compound (I).

EXPERIMENTAL

6-(Thiazyl-2'-) amino-4-hydroxy-3-piperidinomethyl-2-methylquinoline (I, R = piperidino).—To 6-(thiazyl-2'-) amino-4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline (7.1 g.), suspended in aqueous alcohol (90%, 150 c.c.), hydrochloric acid (10%) was added drop by drop under shaking till the clear solution obtained was just acid to Congo red. After adding piperidine (5 g.) and formaldehyde (40% w/v; 4.2 c.c.), the solution was heated under reflux on the water-bath for 15 hours. After distilling off the alcohol under reduced pressure, the residue was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and a brown solid was obtained on basification with cold dilute alkali. It was purified by acid-alkali treatment. It is readily soluble in acetic acid and is not precipitated on dilution with water, indicating the formation of a salt. It is practically insoluble in other organic solvents except in pyridine, in which it is readily soluble even in the cold and could not be crystallised from pyridine. It was therefore washed with hot acetone, hot alcohol and finally with ether, when it was obtained as a brownish solid (6.5 g.) decomposing at 302-304°. (Found: N, 15.34. $C_{18}H_{22}ON_4S$ requires N, 15.82 per cent).

Whereas 6-(thiazyl-2'-) amino-4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline is soluble in cold dilute alkali, the above compound (I, R = piperidino) is insoluble in cold dilute alkali, even on long standing.

6-(Thiazyl-2'-) amino-4-chloro-3-piperidinomethyl-2-methylquinoline (II, R = piperidino).—The above compound (I, R = piperidino; 10 g.) was gradually added to phosphorus oxychloride (50 c.c.), when a thick solution was obtained with rise in temperature. The solution was heated under reflux in an oil-bath at 125°-130° for 4 hours. Next day, excess of phosphorus oxychloride was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue, after being cooled in ice, was treated with cold water, when a dark, clear solution was obtained. On basification with alkali, a brown solid was obtained, which was insoluble in most of the organic solvents. It was, however, soluble in nitrobenzene and was obtained, from nitrobenzene-acetone mixture, as a brownish granular solid (6.2 g.) which turned dark on heating and did not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 14.58. $C_{18}H_{21}N_4S$ requires N, 15.03 per cent).

6-(Thiazyl-2'-) amino-4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethyl-2-methylquinoline (I, R = diethylamino) was similarly prepared as in the case of the previous compound (I, R = piperidino). It was insoluble in most of the organic solvents and was obtained as a brownish granular solid after being washed with hot acetone, hot alcohol and ether. It does not melt even at 300°. (Found: N, 16.03. $C_{20}H_{26}ON_4S$ requires N, 16.37 per cent).

6-Acetylamino-4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethyl-2-methylquinoline (III).—A mixture of 6-acetylamino-4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline (10 g.), diethylamine (7.3 g.) and formaldehyde (40% w/v; 7.5 c.c.) in alcohol (225 c.c.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath for about 4 hours, when gradually a clear solution was obtained, which was

further heated for 7 hours more. On standing overnight in a cold room, a crystalline solid (5.5 g.) was obtained, which was recrystallised from alcohol in colorless, shining rectangular plates. It shrinks and turns yellowish at 190-91° and becomes a viscous mass at 258-60°. (Found : N, 14.26. $C_{17}H_{23}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.95 per cent).

Whereas 6-acetylamino-4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline is practically insoluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid, the above compound (III) is readily soluble.

6-Amino-4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethyl-2-methylquinoline (IV) was obtained by heating for 4 hours under reflux on the water-bath a solution of (III, 12.5 g.) in hydrochloric acid (20%, 100 c.c.), evaporating the solution to dryness and basifying the aqueous solution of the residue with ammonium hydroxide. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone and other organic solvents. It was crystallised from alcohol as an orange crystalline powder, which did not melt even at 300°. (Found : N, 16.54. $C_{18}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 16.21 per cent). It contains a diazotisable amino group.

Thiocyanate of 6-Thiocarbamido-4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethyl-2-methylquinoline (V).—To an aqueous solution of the dihydrochloride (10 g.) of (IV), a concentrated aqueous solution of potassium thiocyanate (7 g.) was added, when a precipitate was immediately obtained, which went into solution on heating on the water-bath. The solution was further heated, when gradually a pasty mass was obtained which soon solidified. The solid was baked on the water-bath for 30 minutes, allowed to cool, triturated with cold water, filtered and thoroughly washed with cold water. It was twice crystallised from hot water as a fine yellow crystalline powder (5.5 g.) melting at 204-205° (decomp.). It was dried at 105°-110° *in vacuo*. (Found : N, 18.96 ; S, 16.43. $C_{18}H_{22}ON_4S$. HCNS requires N, 18.56 ; S, 16.97 per cent).

Its aqueous solution gives a deep red coloration with ferric chloride, which is not discharged by addition of hydrochloric acid but is destroyed by aqueous mercuric chloride. An alcoholic solution of the compound decomposes sodium bicarbonate with evolution of carbon dioxide.

When a hydrochloric acid solution of the above thiocyanate was basified with sodium bicarbonate, the *free base* was obtained as a white pasty mass which, however, could not be induced to crystallise.

Conversion of (V) into 6-(Thiazyl-2'-)amino-4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethyl-2-methylquinoline (I, R=diethylamino).—To a hot aqueous solution of the above compound (V, 7.5 g) $\alpha\beta$ -dichloro-diethyl ether (3.5 g.) was gradually added under shaking and the reaction mixture heated under reflux on the water-bath for 1 hour. On cooling, the solution was diluted with water, washed with ether and basified under cooling with ammonium hydroxide, when a brownish solid was obtained. After purification, as described previously, the compound was confirmed to be identical with (I, R=diethylamino) by a study of its properties and by analysis.

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